

WAYS TO INCREASE THE EFFICIENCY OF DEVELOPING INFORMATION COMPETENCE IN FUTURE PHYSICAL EDUCATION TEACHERS

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Abstract: In this article, ways to train teachers to use information technologies and increase their effectiveness were considered. Based on the analysis of the normative-legal framework and scientific-methodical literature on the studied subject, the specific features of the introduction of information technologies in the study of certain subjects were determined.

Key words: information technologies in education, students, computerization; e-learning, teachers.

Introduction.

At the moment, many citizens of our country are actively interested in the modern education system. Information technologies are used in all aspects of human activity, spread with the help of information flows in society and form the global information space. Today in the world they are more widespread, because society needs to update information. Information technologies are used in almost all spheres of society's life. Central to this process is the computerization of education. Today, the Ministry of Public Education of the Republic of Uzbekistan pays great attention to the informatization of the educational process, because the use of information technologies significantly increases the pedagogical methods of teaching students [1].

Computer technologies have entered and are entering all spheres of human activity. It is impossible to imagine any industry in which electronic computers are not used. The education sector is no exception and has gone through the process of computerization. In addition, computers are considered not as an additional means of learning, but as an integral part of the educational process, designed to significantly increase its effectiveness [2].

The global goal of informatization of education is to radically improve the quality of education that meets the requirements of the post-industrial society. The global goal is multifactorial and includes a number of sub-goals: preparing students for full and effective participation in all aspects of life in the information society, improving the quality of education, increasing the level of convenience of education, national The information integration of the education system is developing on the basis of the infrastructure of the world community.

Discussion and Results

A prerequisite for the effective integration of information technologies into the educational process is the presence of a management multimedia environment between the teacher and the student, the structure of which includes all components of information technologies and a single interactive method of access to them.

Among the didactic principles influenced by the pedagogical technologies of educational informatization are the following:

- the principle of activity; principle of independence;
- the principle of combining collective and individual forms of educational work;
- principle of motivation;
- the principle of connection between theory and practice;
- efficiency principle [3].

Analysis of the current stage of development of information technologies, their use in education made it possible to identify conflicts between the technical and software capabilities of modern computers, global and local networks, and the level of their use.

In the face of the rapid changes taking place in our society, the educational system is faced with the difficult task of forming a new mentality of a person who can adapt to modern economic, information-social, ecological and spiritual-ethical requirements. Any methodology or pedagogical technology describes how to process and transmit information so that it is best learned by the student. That is, any pedagogical technology is an information technology, which can change depending on the changes in the information means of education, the form and goals of education [1].

Consider some of the problems of applying new information technologies in the professional activities of future teachers:

- issues of effective use of telecommunications and information technologies in education remain open;
- the need to use information technologies in education is not justified;
- there is no systematic research on what knowledge, skills and qualifications should be formed among pedagogues in order to use multimedia technologies in practical activities;
- also, the methodology of teaching new information technologies to teachers has not been developed;
- the methodology of learning various subjects using multimedia educational tools has not been developed;
- there are no methods of quantitative assessment of the level of mastering of knowledge, skills, and competences in the use of information technologies;
- methodological problem of presenting the content of educational material.

Methodological problems of presenting the content of the educational material are one of the main reasons for the gap between the potential and real possibilities of using information and telecommunication technologies in education today. Solving these problems lags behind the rapid pace of development of information and telecommunication technologies and requires serious attention. The fact that the educational material is not developed with the correct information makes it difficult to use the unique opportunities of modern information technologies in teaching. There is a need to address the challenges associated with an active approach to learning that requires different structures to deliver learning material.

It should be noted that when planning and developing the content of the educational material, it is necessary to take into account the main three components of the teacher's activity - presentation of the educational material, practice, feedback. Changing the content of education requires the teacher to have high professional and information competence,

knowledge in the fields of pedagogy, psychology, informatics, and mathematics. The teacher should transfer all his knowledge to the basis of modern pedagogical teaching technologies, including development and implementation.

The introduction of new information technologies into education requires the training of new pedagogic personnel who are able to constantly update the ideas and content of education, comprehensively study new technologies and put them into practice. It is necessary to develop a methodology for teaching future science teachers to use information technologies.

A graduate of a higher educational institution of pedagogy should perfectly master the mechanism of information search, collection and processing, be able to visually perceive the expression of ideas, concepts, processes, and express his opinion by using various types of information. The important tasks of training future teachers studying at a pedagogical higher educational institution are to master computer technologies and be able to use them in learning and teaching science.

In the practice of higher educational institutions of pedagogy, there is almost no experience of organizing such a course, which serves as an environment for the active use of new information technologies as a tool of knowledge in the educational process. There are several attempts to use computer technology as a teaching tool in the learning process in the study of general technical subjects. Consequently, this problem is not sufficiently developed (one-sided) in pedagogical universities [2].

An important direction of computer use in the educational process is to monitor students' knowledge and skills. Practice shows that 93% of teachers and 84% of students are not satisfied with the existing knowledge assessment system, however, the transition to the knowledge assessment rating system and pedagogical monitoring system is slow.

The use of new information technologies increases the effectiveness of teaching students of higher educational institutions of pedagogy, if:

- criteria for the selection of the content of computer modeling systems in relation to the educational process for students have been developed;
- the content of program-pedagogical systems is highlighted and methods of using information media are selected;
- adaptation of computer modeling and design systems to the educational process was carried out;
- it is shown that the use of computer modeling systems in the educational process for students of pedagogical higher educational institutions serves to improve their informational, professional and methodological preparation, as well as to develop the skills of scientific and research work.

The use of new information technologies leads to the solution of acute problems of modern education, in which the development of the technological subsystem of education has a significant impact on all other subsystems: pedagogical, organizational, economic, and even theoretical and methodological. The fundamentals of the system are accompanied by fundamental changes.

Thus, informatization of education leads to changes in certain aspects of the educational process. The activity of the student and the teacher is moving to information. The student can use a large amount of different information, collect and process it. The teacher will be freed from regular classes and will have the opportunity to study the learning process and monitor

the student's progress. In general, teachers are not ready to switch from teaching methods formed in the educational process to the use of information technologies. Computers are mainly used as supplementary teaching aids.

The use of information technologies helps to improve educational activities, increases the quality of the educational process, and increases the effectiveness of individual activities of students. Also, the use of information technologies in the educational process prepares qualified specialists for the development and application of modern technologies and tools of educational informatization.

Analyzing modern trends in the development of educational informatization, rational organization based on the interests of the future scientific-technical, socio-economic and spiritual development of society creates a complex and extremely relevant scientific, organizational and social problem. In order to solve this problem, it is necessary to have continuous cooperation of experts in the field of education, as well as effective support of this cooperation by the state.

Conclusion.

In addition to the main educational task, information technology develops the student's creative abilities and expands his worldview. In addition to basic subjects, a student can get additional education, for example, start learning a programming language, use online courses, simulators and communicate on any social network. You can get education regardless of your place of residence and age. Currently, the worldwide network and various software products are diverse in their range. It is precisely because of the development of information technologies that the idea of continuing additional education is fully realized. Also, information technologies encourage more people to learn, to carry out various research projects, to create innovative projects and articles.

In conclusion, the use of information technologies in the educational process is necessary to prepare students for life and work in the modern information society.

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